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Master thesis

Isolation of bioactive compounds and evaluation of their anti-biofilm properties from *Neonothopanus nambi* collected in Kenya

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Abbreviations list

μm	Micrometer
μL	Microliter
ACN	acetonitrile
ACT	acetone
AMR	antimicrobial resistance
BLAST	basic local alignment search tool
CASO	casein-soy-pepton
CD	circular dichroism
CF	cystic fibrosis
CM	complete minimal
CV	crystal violet
EDTA	ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid
ESI	electrospray ionization
EtOAc	ethyl acetate
EtOH	ethanol
EPS	extracellular polymeric substances
F	fraction
GLASS	Global Antimicrobial Resistance and Use Surveillance System
h	hour
HGT	horizontal gene transfer
HPLC	High performance liquid chromatography
HR-ESIMS	high-resolution electrospray ionization mass spectrometry
IC	inhibitory concentration
LCMS	liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry
m	mycelium
M	molar
MAA	microporenic acid A
min	minute
mL	milliliter
MeOH	methanol

MIC	minimum inhibitory concentration
MDR	multi drug resistance
MRSA	methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
MS	mass spectrometer/spectrometry
m/z	mass divided by charge number
NIH	national institutes of health
NMR	nuclear magnetic resonance
OD	optical density
PBS	phosphate-buffered saline
PCR	polymerase chain reaction
pH	potential of hydrogen
QS	quorum sensing
RP	reversed phase
rpm	revolutions per minute
RT	room temperature
s	supernatant
SYM	sucrose yeast malt
UV	ultraviolet
VGT	vertical gene transfer
YM	yeast malt
ZM	Zucker medium

1 Introduction

Since the discovery of antibiotics, especially the “Golden Age” of massive antibiotics discovery from the 1940s to the 1960s, the death and infections caused by microorganisms have significantly decreased. The rapid and easy discovery of antibiotics led to excessive use, which caused significant global public health issues in Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR) (Hutchings et al. 2019), as effective antimicrobial therapeutics are crucial for treatment of infections and many modern medical practices. According to Global Antimicrobial Resistance and Use Surveillance System (GLASS) Report 2022, AMR rates rose by over 15% in 2020 compared to 2017 in certain regions and for specific pathogens (Miethke et al. 2021). Another statistical estimate from 2019 estimated that bacterial AMR was directly contributed to around 4.95 million deaths (Antimicrobial Resistance Collaborators 2022). Considering the planktonic cell level, the exceptional ability driven by vertical gene transfer (VGT) and horizontal gene transfer (HGT) of bacteria to develop resistance is undeniable (Catalano et al. 2022; Davies 2006), formation of biofilms by various infectious agents further exacerbates the situation. Biofilms pose a significant challenge in treating chronic infections due to their enhanced resistance to antibiotics and the host immune response (Gondil et al. 2023).

Biofilms are highly intricate in terms of their structure, function and impact on health and disease. Biofilms are mainly defined as stable microbial communities that are encased in extracellular polymeric substances (EPS). They are characterized by the irreversible attachment of microbial cells to surfaces, substrates, or one another, all embedded within the EPS matrix. This arrangement leads to distinct phenotypic expressions in terms of gene transcription and growth rates. A biofilm may consist of a single type of microorganism or a diverse mixture of bacteria, fungi, archaea, protozoa, and yeasts. Additionally, biofilms possess a channel-like structure that regulates the exchange of gases, nutrients, and antimicrobial agents (Davies 2003; Zhao et al. 2023).

Biofilms can inhabit a wide range of both biotic and abiotic surfaces (Stoodley et al. 2004). Sufficient supply of nutrients, adequate humidity and suitable temperature conditions make an optimal environment for bacterial biofilms to grow. Therefore, humans provide an ideal source of biotic microenvironments for bacterial colonization and biofilm formation, frequently resulting in infectious diseases (Høiby 2014).

As reported by the National Institutes of Health, roughly 80% of microbial infections have a biofilm-related origin (Guzman-Soto et al. 2021). The situation is deteriorating further as the development pipeline for innovative drugs is nearly empty. Less than 25% of current drugs in the clinical development pipeline act through a novel mechanism and none potentially active against WHO critical threat pathogens (Miethke et al. 2021). New antimicrobial agents displaying innovative chemistry and novel mode of actions are desperately needed worldwide.

Figure 1. A schematic depiction of steps of bacterial biofilms. (A) Reversible attachment (B) Irreversible attachment (C) Cell division and EPS secretion (D) Maturation (E) Dispersal (Zhao et al., 2023).

Bacterial microorganisms attach to surfaces as the first stage of biofilm formation. Van der Waals forces, electrostatic forces, and hydrophobic interactions primarily influence adhesion, although this adhesion is weak and reversible (Carniello et al. 2018). Surface characteristics such as roughness, hydrophobicity, surface charge, and film formation significantly influence how efficiently bacteria can colonize and form biofilms (Tuson and Weibel 2013). The second phase of bacterial biofilm formation involves irreversible adhesion, where microbial cells permanently adhere to surfaces through various bonding mechanisms like hydrophobic interactions, hydrogen bonding, covalent bonding, ionic bonding, and dipole-dipole interactions (Carniello et al. 2018). At this stage, the Quorum Sensing (QS) system plays a critical role in biofilm formation by enabling bacteria to communicate using chemical signals, facilitating coordinated behavior (Abraham 2016). The third stage of bacterial biofilm formation involves the synthesis and secretion of extracellular polymeric substances (EPS). EPS is a hydrophobic substrate that enhances bacterial condensation and biofilm adhesion. It plays a vital role in various processes such as surface adhesion, biofilm structural development, cell-to-cell communication, nutrient acquisition, signal transduction, and genetic

information exchange (Costa et al. 2018). EPS matrix is also rich in enzymes, protein structures such as fimbriae, extracellular DNA (eDNA) which aids in connecting bacterial cells and lipids which can influence the adhesion of certain bacteria like *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans* (Flemming et al. 2016). The fourth stage of biofilm development is maturation, during which bacterial biofilms become more complex as bacteria replicate within the EPS matrix, forming microbial colonies and three-dimensional structures. As these colonies grow, gene expression changes, promoting further EPS production. Once the matrix is well-formed, water channels develop, functioning similarly to a circulatory system by transporting nutrients to the bacterial community and removing waste (Zhao et al. 2023). The final stage of biofilm development is dispersal, where bacterial cells are released from the mature biofilm and can spread to infect other areas, forming new biofilms. Although dispersal mechanisms vary depending on the bacteria, they generally involve three key processes: detachment of cells from colonies, transfer of these cells to other locations, and attachment to new substrates, initiating the formation of new biofilm structures (Shen et al. 2018).

Discovery of the penicillin is one of the most significant breakthroughs in history of medicine which propelled fungi in eminent positions in research endeavors (Chain et al. 1940). Fungi have been continually proved as potential reservoir of novel bioactive compounds with pharmaceutical applications as evident by many discoveries of blockbusters such as lefamulin, fingolimod, pleuromutilins, or enfumafungin, a fungal metabolite recently culminated into development of Ibrexafungerp (Mapook et al. 2022). The secondary metabolome of fungi represents a vast and diverse reservoir of natural compounds that remains largely unexplored. Secondary metabolites are chemical compounds synthesized by organisms that serve functions beyond those directly related to growth, development, or reproduction thus, enhancing the organism's ability to survive in a specific environment (Reshi et al. 2023). These compounds display a broad spectrum of bioactivities, including antifungal, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer effects, making them invaluable contributors to drug discovery with medical, industrial, and agricultural importance (Manganyi et al. 2020).

Figure 2. Timeline showing the decade new classes of antibiotic reached the clinic. The antibiotics are coloured per their source: green = actinomycetes, blue = other bacteria, purple = fungi and orange = synthetic. At the bottom of the timeline are key dates relating to antibiotic discovery and antimicrobial resistance, including the first reports of drug-resistant strains methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA), vancomycin-resistant enterococci (VRE), vancomycin-resistant *S. aureus* (VRSA) and plasmid-borne colistin resistance in Enterobacteriaceae (Hutchings et al., 2019).

In this thesis, a strain of the basidiomycete species *Neonothopanus nambi*, which was isolated from Arabuko Sokoke National Park, Kenya, was analyzed for production of secondary metabolites with further evaluation of the bioactivity of isolated compounds through the Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC), cytotoxicity assays and biofilm assays thereby identifying the promising candidates for further investigation as anti-biofilm compounds.

Argentinian naturalist Carlo Luigi Speggazzini first described the species in 1883 as *Agaricus nambi*, which was later transferred to *Pleurotus nambi* (Saccardo 1887) and *Dendrodarcus nambi* (Kuntze 1898). In 1999, Ronald H. Peterson and Irmgard Krisai reclassified the fungus into a new genus, *Neonothopanus*, belongs to family *Omphalotaceae*, order *Agaricales*, class *Agaricomycetes*, phylum *Basidiomycota*. Compounds reported from this species are for example Nambinones and Aurisins, which exhibit significant bioactivities, including antimalarial effects against *Plasmodium falciparum*,

antimycobacterial activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, outstanding anti-MRSA activity and a varying range of cytotoxicity (Peterson RH et al. 1999; Kanokmedhakul et al. 2012). Other studies also elucidated the efficiency of bioactive compounds from *N. nambi* against root-rot disease (Wisetsai et al. 2023).

N. nambi produces diverse secondary metabolites based on the condition of its culture. The vary production of sesterterpenoids, sesquiterpenoids and their dimer, as well as terphenyls and benzonated reported before are shown below.

Figure 3. Structures of reported scalarane sesterterpenoids, nambiscalaranes (**1 - 8**) from *N. nambi* (Wisetsai et al. 2021).

Figure 4. Structures of terphenyls **9 - 11**. (Sangsopha et al. 2019)

Figure 5. Structures of sesquiterpenoids (**12 - 17**) and their dimer (**18 - 21**). (Sangsopha et al. 2019; Kanokmedhakul et al. 2012)

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Figure 1. Structures of sesquiterpenoids **22**. (Kanokmedhakul et al. 2012)

2 Material and Methods

Table 1: Devices used

Devices	Model	Manufacturer
Autoclave	Dampfsterilisator 9-6-9 HSI FD	Westima Sauter KG; Köln, Germany
Autoclave	Systec VX-150	Systec GmbH; Wettenberg (Germany)
Analytical HPLCs	Agilent 1260 Infinity Series	Agilent Technologies Deutschland GmbH;
	Agilent 1100 Series	Böblingen (Germany)
Camera	EOS 5D Mark IV	Canon Deutschland GmbH; Krefeld (Germany)
CD-spectrometer	J-815	Jasco Deutschland GmbH; Pfungstadt, Germany
Centrifuge for reaction vessels (15 or 50 mL)	Rotofix 32 A	Andreas Hettich GmbH & Co. KG; Tuttlingen (Germany)
Circular polarimeter	MCP 150	Anton Paar Group AG; Graz (Austria)
Cleanbench	HERAsafe® HS12	Heraeus Holding GmbH; Hanau (German)
Cleanbench	Herasafe™ 2030i 1.5	Thermo Fisher Scientific Waltham, MA (USA)
Evaporator 4mL Vials	ECHM-12-32	Gebr. Liebisch GmbH & Co. KG; Bielefeld (Germany)
Evaporator 4mL Vials	EVA-EC1-24-S	VLM Korrosions-Prüftechnik, Labortechnik & Dienstleistungen GmbH; Lippstadt, Germany
Homogenizer	T25 easy clean digital	IKA®-Werke GmbH & Co. KG; Staufen (Germany)
	ULTRATURRAX®	
Homogenizer	S 25N-25F	IKA®-Werke GmbH & Co. KG; Staufen (Germany)
Incubation shaker	Multitron 50mm	Infors AG; Bottmingen (Switzerland)
Ion trap mass spectrometer	amaZon speed™	Bruker Daltonics GmbH; Bremen (Germany)
Magnetic stirrer	Magnetrührer KMO 2 basic I- KAMAG®	IKA® -Werke GmbH & Co. KG
	Research Plus	
Manual pipettes	0.5 - 10 µL	Eppendorf Vertrieb Deutschland GmbH; Wesseling-Berzdorf (Germany)
	10 - 100 µL	
	20 - 200 µL	
	100 – 1000 µL	

NMR spectrometer	Bruker Avance III 700 (¹ H 700 MHz, ¹³ C 175 MHz) Bruker Avance III 500 (¹ H 500 MHz, ¹³ C 125 MHz)	Bruker Daltonik GmbH; Bremen, Germany
N ₂ -Evaporator	ECHM-12-32	Gebr. Liebisch GmbH & Co. KG; Bielefeld (Germany)
pH-Meter	inoLab [®] pH 7110	WTW Wissenschaftlich – Technische Werkstätten GmbH; Weilheim (Germany)
Preparative HPLCs	Gilson PLC 2250 Purification system Gilson PLC 2050 Purification system	Gilson, Inc.; Middletown (WI, USA)
Precision balance	CUBIS [®] MCA225P-2S00-U	Sartorius AG; Göttingen (Germany)
Quick scale	Cubis MSE, MSE623P-100-DE	Sartorius AG; Göttingen (Germany)
Rotary evaporator	Hei – VAP ML/G3B Rotavac Vario Control	Heidolph Instruments GmbH & Co. KG; Schwabach (Germany)
UV-Vis Spectrometer	UV-2450 (RC)	Shimadzu Corporation; Kyoto (Japan)
Ultrapure water system	Milli-Q Direct	Merck Chemicals GmbH; Darmstadt (Germany)
Ultrasonic bath	Sonorex Digital 10 P	BANDELIN electronic GmbH & Co. KG; Berlin (Germany)
UV-Vis spectrometer	UV-2450	Shimadzu Corporation; Kyōto (Japan)
Vortex	MS 3 digital	IKA [®] -Werke GmbH & Co. KG; Staufen (Germany)
Zentrifuge	4-16 KS	Sigma Laboratory Centrifuges GmbH; Osterode am Harz (Germany)
Glucose-Teststreifen	Medi-Test Glucose	Macherey-Nagel GmbH & Co. KG; Düren, Deutschland
96-well plates	TPP tissue culture ref.no 92196	TPP Techno Plastic Products AG, Zollstrasse 7, CH-8219 Trasadingen, Switzerland
XAD beads	Amberlite™ XAD [®] -2	SIGMA-ALDRICH CHEMIE GmbH, Steinheim, Germany
Seperation Seesand	Seesand, -50 +70 mesh, suitable for chromatography	SIGMA-ALDRICH CHEMIE GmbH, Steinheim, Germany

Table 2: Chromatographic devices

Devices	Model	Manufacturer
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Analytical HPLC system	Dionex UltiMate® 3000 Series	Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc.;Waltham, Massachusetts (USA)
Analytical HPLC system	Agilent 1260 Infinity II LC System	Agilent Technologies Deutschland GmbH; Böblingen, Germany
ESI-ITMS	AmaZon speed™	Bruker Daltonics GmbH & Co. KG; Bremen (Germany)
HR-ESIMS	MaXis	Bruker Daltonics GmbH & Co. KG; Bremen (Germany)
Preparative HPLC system	Gilson PLC 2250	Gilson, Inc.; Middleton; WI, (USA)
Semi preparative HPLC system	Agilent 1200 Infinity Series	Agilent Technologies Deutschland GmbH; Böblingen (Germany)
Trapped Ion Mobility Spectrometry (TIMS) (Method: HR-MS)	timsTOF Pro2	Bruker Daltonics GmbH; Bremen (Germany)

Table 3: Chromatography columns

Column name	Size	Manufacturer
Waters X-Bridge C18	Preparative:	
Aquity UPLC BEH C-18	250 x 19 mm, 5 µm	Waters Corporation,
	Semi-preparative:	Germany
	250 x 10 mm, 5 µm	
	Analytical:	
	50 x 2.1mm 1.7 µm	
Nucleodur Phenyl – Hexyl_RP	Preparative:	Macherey-Nagel, Düren,
	250 x 40 mm, 5 µm	Germany
	250 x 21.1 mm, 5 µm	
	Analytical:	
	250 x 10 mm, 5 µm	

Table 4: Media and chemicals used

Media	Ingredient	Concentration [in g/L]	Type	pH-value	Manufacturer
Q6 1/2	D-Glucose	2,5	liquid	7.2	Cerestar Deutschland GmbH; Krefeld, Germany

	Glycerol	10			Carl Roth GmbH & Co. KG; Karlsruhe, Germany
	Cotton seed flour	5			Sigma-Aldrich Chemie GmbH; Steinheim am Albuch, Germany
	D-Glucose	4			Cerestar, Deurotschland GmbH
	Malt extract	10	liquid		Gibco, Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc.; Ma, USA
YM6.3	Yeast extract	4		6.3	Organotechnie; La Courneuve France
	Agar	20		For YM6.3 agar	Becton, Dickinson and Company; Sparks, USA
	Yeast extract	4			Organotechnie; La Courneuve France
	D-Glucose	1.5			Cerestar Deutschland GmbH; Krefeld, Germany
	Edamine	0.5			Thermo Fisher Scientific Oxoid Ltd.; Hampshire, UK
ZM1/2	Mannitol	4	liquid	7.2	Cal Roth GmbH + Co. KG; Karlsruhe, Germany
	Molasses	5			Nordzucker AG; Braunschweig, Germany
	(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	0.5			Merck KGaA; Darmstadt, Germany
	Oatmeal	5			Herrnmühle; Reichelsheim, Germany
	Sucrose	4			Carl Roth GmbH & Co. KG; Karlsruhe, Germany
	Dextrin	40			Cal Roth GmbH + Co. KG; Karlsruhe, Germany
	Glucose	10			Cerestar Deutschland GmbH; Krefeld, Germany
GDYP	Yeast extract	4	liquid	3	Organotechnie; La Courneuve France
	Soy peptone	2			Becton Dickinson and Company, le Pont de Claix, France
	KH ₂ PO ₄	2			Carl Roth GmbH & Co. KG; Karlsruhe, Germany
	FeCl ₃ x 6 H ₂ O	2			Merck KgaA, Darmstadt, Germany

	MgSO ₄ x 7 H ₂ O	0,5			Merck KgaA, Darmstadt, Germany
CM	Cornmeal	20	liquid	5,5	Frießinger Mühle GmbH, Bad Wimpfen, Germany
	Glucose	4			Cerestar Deutschland GmbH; Krefeld, Germany
SYM	Malt extract	30	liquid	6,3	Gibco, Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc.; Ma, USA
	Saccharose	10			Organotechnie; La Courneuve France
	Yeast extract	5			
SYMglu	Malt extract	30	Liquid	6.3	Gibco, Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc.; Ma, USA
	Glucose	10			Cerestar Deutschland GmbH; Krefeld, Germany
	Yeast extract	5			Organotechnie; La Courneuve France
SNL	D(+)-Glucose-monohydrate	30.0	Liquid	6,0	Cerestar Deutschland GmbH; Krefeld, Germany
	L-Asparagine-monohydrate	4,5			SERVA Electrophoresis GmbH, Heideberg, Germany
	KH ₂ PO ₄	1,5			Carl Roth GmbH & Co. KG; Karlsruhe, Germany
	MgSO ₄ x 7H ₂ O	0,5			Merck KgaA, Darmstadt, Germany
	Yeast extract	3,0			Organotechnie; La Courneuve France
	Trace Element Solution	1,0 mL			/
Rice media	Rice	100 mg	solid	-	Oryza Ideal Reis Langkorn parboiled (500 g), Euryza GmbH, Hamburg, Germany
	Distilled water	200 mL			/
CASO	Peptone from casein	15	liquid	7.3	Sigma-Aldrich GmbH; Taufkirchen, Germany
	Peptone from soymeal	5			Sigma-Aldrich GmbH; Taufkirchen, Germany
	NaCl	5			Thermo Fisher Scientific; Fair Lawn, USA

10 x PBS	NaCl	100	liquid	7.4	Thermo Fisher Scientific; Fair Lawn, USA
	KCl	2,5			Avantor-Leistungsmaterialien; Griesheim, Germany
	K ₂ HPO ₄	3			Sigma Medical Technology GmbH, Steinbach (Taunus), Germany
	Na ₂ HPO ₄	18			
Trace Elemen t Solutio n	FeCl ₃ x 6 H ₂ O	80mg	liquid	-	Merck KgaA, Darmstadt, Germany
	ZnSO ₄ x 7 H ₂ O	90mg			MP Biomedicals, LLC, Fountain Parkway, Solon; Parc d'Innovation, Illkirch, France
	MnSO ₄ x H ₂ O	30mg			Merck KgaA, Darmstadt, Germany
	CuSO ₄ x 5 H ₂ O	5mg			Merck KgaA, Darmstadt, Germany
	EDTA	400 mg			Sigma Medical Technology GmbH, Steinbach (Taunus), Germany

Table 5: Other chemicals used

Chemical	note	Company
Acetone, CH ₃ COCH ₃	99,9%, BAKER analyzed	Avantor-Leistungsmaterialien; Griesheim, Germany
Acetonitrile, C ₂ H ₃ N	≥99,9%, BAKER HPLC analyzed	Avantor-Leistungsmaterialien; Griesheim, Germany
Crystal violet	For cell staining	Sigma-Aldrich GmbH; Taufkirchen, Germany
Ethyl acetate, C ₄ H ₈ O ₂	99,9%, BAKER Ultra Resi- analyzed	Avantor-Leistungsmaterialien; Griesheim, Germany
Potassium chloride, KCl	99,9%, BAKER analyzed	Avantor-Leistungsmaterialien; Griesheim, Germany
Methanol, CH ₄ O	≥99,9%, BAKER HPLC analyzed	Avantor-Leistungsmaterialien; Griesheim, Germany
Sodium chloride, NaCl	99%	Thermo Fisher Scientific; Fair Lawn, USA
Sodium sulfate, Na ₂ SO ₄	99%	Thermo Fisher Scientific; Fair Lawn, USA

3 Methods

3.1 Prescreening of the secondary metabolite production in the fungi from the species *Neonothopanus nambi*

3.1.1 Collection of fungal strains

The fruiting bodies of *N. nambi* were collected on 11 May 2022 in Arabuko Sokoke Park, Kenya, Africa; by Hedda Schrey and Jan Peer Wennrich (Helmholtz-Zentrum für Infektionsforschung), later isolated and deposited in Prague. CCC Nr.1560.

3.1.2 Fungal strain maintenance and pre-cultivation in liquid and on solid media

N. nambi strain CCC1560 was maintained at RT on YM 6.3 agar plates enveloped with parafilm in dark. Three 5 mm² sections of mycelium cultured on YM 6.3 agar were used to inoculate 200 mL YM 6.3 liquid medium (Table 4). Cultivation took place at 23°C and 140 min⁻¹ in the dark, served as culture for subsequent screening (Section 3.1.2) and scale-up fermentation (Section 3.2.1). Strain was transferred onto new YM 6.3 agar plates every 30 days to prevent contamination.

Fungal-bacterial co-culture with *Chitinophaga pinensis* was accomplished by Nina Sandmann (HZI, MWIS group).

3.1.3 Screening of secondary metabolites production of *Neonothopanus nambi*

The strain CCC 1560 was cultured on diverse media to investigate the optimal growth conditions and the resultant diversity of secondary metabolites. Liquid media, namely YM6.3, ZM/2, Q6/2, SNL, SYM, SYMglu, GDYP, CM, as well as solid-state cultivation media, including rice and YM6.3, were prepared as detailed in Table 4.

Liquid media (200 mL) was inoculated in a 500 mL flask with 3 pieces mycelium-agar transferred from an overgrown agar plate. The flasks were incubated at 23 °C with continuous shaking at 140 rpm and were harvested after 5 and 7 days respectively post the complete glucose consumption. Glucose levels were monitored daily using Medi-Test Glucose strips (Machery-Nagel®, Düren, Germany).

For solid-state cultivation, 100 g of rice with 100 mL deionized water in a 500 mL flask served as the substrate. Inoculation was performed with 10 mL of homogenized preculture grown in YM 6.3 media cultivation (section 3.1.2). Harvesting occurred after two, three, and four weeks of incubation, depending on the growth of fungi.

3.1.4 Extraction of fungi grown in small scale different liquid media

For the extraction of fungi cultivated in small scale liquid media, mycelium was separated from supernatant using centrifuge. The Supernatant underwent three times extractions using a biphasic system of water and ethyl acetate (1:1) within a separation funnel. Water phase was discarded. After drying organic phase with anhydrous sodium sulfate, it was transferred into round bottom flask and evaporated to dryness through rotary evaporator at 40 degrees Celsius.

The mycelia were extracted with acetone, followed by three times 30-minute ultrasonic baths at 40°C and 100% intensity. After evaporation of the filtered acetone using a rotary evaporator, the remaining aqueous phases were extracted three times by adding an equal volume of ethyl acetate in a separatory funnel. The resulting organic phase was dried using anhydrous sodium sulfate, followed by filtration and evaporation under vacuum in a rotary evaporator.

The obtained crude extracts from supernatant and mycelia were first filtered through a cartridge column (Strata TM-X 33 µm Polymeric Reversed Phase 1 g / 20 mL, Giga Tubes) using acetonitrile, methanol and acetone in sequence to remove insoluble impurities and fatty acids and afterward were transferred to round bottom flasks for evaporating solvent to dryness, different vials were prepared respectively according to different cartridge solution used, mycelia and supernatant. Vials were dried with nitrogen dryer and stored under minus 20 degrees Celsius thereafter.

3.1.5 Extraction of secondary metabolites from solid-state fermentation

4 YM 6.3 agar plates with fungi were cut into small pieces fully immersing under acetone for 3 times 30 min-sonication at 40 °C with an intensity of 100 %, and all acetone was collected and evaporated. The later water phase extraction and evaporation process was same as the process of mycelium extraction (section 3.1.4).

3.2 Scale up of the fermentation and isolation of compounds

3.2.1 Scale-up fermentations

YM medium was selected for the first scale-up fermentation based on the crude extract yield and promising MS peaks. Liquid cultivation of CCC 1560 in YM 6.3 was carried out in 24 500mL flasks each containing 200 mL of medium. They were inoculated with 10 mL homogenized seed culture (1 flask of YM 6.3 200mL liquid cultivation) and incubated at 23 °C with continuous shaking at 140 rpm. Compounds from mycelium and supernatant were analyzed separately.

For the second scale up, in total 5L YM and 5L SNL media were prepared. 1300 mL of YM 6.3 and SNL media were respectively prepared and autoclaved in eight 2000 mL flasks, each media contains four flasks. Other processes were the same as above described.

3.2.2 Extraction of the secondary metabolites from first and second scale-up fermentation

To extract products from the scaled-up fermentation process, 4 L of supernatant was treated with 1–2% XAD resin beads (40–80 mg) and stirred for 3 to 5 hours. Following this, the beads were collected and washed three times with acetone. The acetone fractions were pooled and evaporated until only the aqueous phase remained. The aqueous phase was then processed according to the mycelium extraction protocol outlined in section 3.1.4. Mycelia were treated as the procedures described in section 3.1.4.

To enhance the efficiency of the purification process using the reversed-phase column, mycelial and supernatant crude extracts were filtered and separated through SPE column Giga Tubes (Strata TM-X 33 µm Polymeric Reversed Phase 1 g / 20 mL, Giga tubes). Mycelial crude extracts were filtered through water-40%ACN, 50-100%ACN, MeOH, ACT fraction; Supernatant crude extracts were filtered through water, 20%ACN, 40%ACN, 50-100%ACN, MeOH, ACT and collected. Some of these fractions were subjected to size-exclusion chromatography as described in section 3.3.2.

3.3 Liquid Chromatography and mass spectrometry (LC-MS) for fractionation

3.3.1 Analytical high-performance liquid chromatography

All crude extracts, as well as fractions obtained through high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), were subjected to analysis using the HPLC System UltiMate® 3000 Series uHPLC (Thermo Fisher Scientific®, Waltman, MA, USA) coupled with an ion trap mass spectrometer (amazon speed™ by Bruker). Crude extracts were dissolved in acetonitrile to achieve a concentration of 5 mg/mL. Separated fractions achieved a concentration of 1mg/mL. 2 µL of each sample were injected onto an Acquity-UPLC® BEH C18 column (2.1 x 50 mm; 1.7 µm). H₂O and acetonitrile (ACN) with 0.1 % formic acid were used as solvents. With a flow rate of 600 µL/min the gradient initiated at 5 % H₂O for 5 min, increased to 100 % ACN in 20 min and remained at that level for an additional 5 minutes. The resulting chromatograms were analyzed using Bruker Data analysis 4.2 software (Bruker Daltonics GmbH & Co KG.).

For a selection of most suitable separation column, pre-test was tried using Agilent 1260 Infinity II system. Columns Waters X-Bridge C18, Aquity UPLC BEH C-18, Nucleodur Phenyl - Hexyl_RP were selected for further separation.

3.3.2 Size-chromatography

Fractions, including 75.39 mg of 20% ACN-SPE-filtered supernatant crude extract combined with 78.05 mg of 40% ACN-SPE-filtered mycelial crude extract, 180 mg of 50–100% ACN-SPE-filtered mycelial crude extract, and 100% ACN-SPE-filtered supernatant crude extract from the first scale-up fermentation, these three rounds were separated individually using a size-exclusion chromatography system (Cytiva OptiRun™ Services Preventive Maintenance PM Record), with 100% MeOH and 0.1% formic acid (FA) as the solvent. All resulting fractions were subsequently combined for further purified using a semi-preparative HPLC system.

3.3.3 Preparative HPLC and MS for the first and second scale-up fermentation

These fractions were analyzed by reverse-phase liquid chromatography (RP-LC) with deionized water (solvent A) and acetonitrile (ACN) (solvent B).

For processing, previously gained fractions were separated on a Gilson RP-HPLC system (Middleton, Wisconsin, USA). The system was equipped with a GX-271 Liquid handler, a diode array detector (DAD) 172 together with a 305 and 306 pump. A Nucleodur Phenyl-Hexyl_RP (250 x 40 mm, 5 μ m; Waters Corporation, Germany) column was used for the process of first scale-up in YM 6.3 media, which was performed with a flow rate of 35 mL/min. Fractions were combined according to the UV absorption at 235, 260, 280, 300, 330 nm.

Combined separation of supernatant and mycelia from second scale-up fermentation was completed using Waters X-bridge C18 column through Gilson system. Per injection is about 200 mg. UV absorption was set as same as above.

3.3.4 Semi-preparative HPLC

Different gradients were used with a column packed with Waters X-Bridge C18 250*10mm 5 μ m (Waters Corporation, Germany) performed with a flowrate of 3 mL/min. All pure compounds were collected according to the UV Absorption at 230, 270, 300, 330 nm from recombined fraction of both first and second scale-up fermentation, gradients were shown in 9.5. After evaporation of ACN in vacuo, the residues were transferred into 4 mL brown vials and measured.

3.3.5 Stability test of the crude extracts

Crude extract stability was tested in different solution, namely ACN, MeOH, ACT. These three vials were tested in Amazon on the same days. Afterward they were stored in heating box at temperature 40 °C overnight. After 24 hours, these three vials were again tested in Amazon. Results would be compared.

3.4 Structure elucidation

3.4.1 High resolution mass spectrometry

To determine the corresponding molecular formula, high-resolution mass data were obtained using an HPLC-coupled mass spectrometer (timsTOF, Bruker). For this purpose, 2 μ L of the pure compounds at the concentration of 0.1 mg/mL were injected into high resolution mass spectrometry system. The gradient started at 5 % H₂O for 0.5 min increasing to 100 % ACN in 19.5 min and maintaining for 5 min with a flow rate of 0.6 mL/min. In contrast to the amazon speedTM-mass

spectrometer, ionization occurs by default in positive mode only. The timsTOF-mass spectrometer is a time-of-flight mass spectrometer (QTOF-MS). The resulting positive mass spectra were evaluated.

3.4.2 NMR spectroscopic analysis

For structural elucidation of the isolated pure compounds, NMR spectra were recorded using a Bruker Avance III 500 (Bruker®, Billerica, MA, USA; ¹H-NMR: 500 MHz; ¹³C-NMR: 125 MHz) spectrometer as well as on an Avance III 700 (Bruker®, Billerica, MA, USA; ¹H-NMR: 700 MHz, ¹³C: 175 MHz) with cryo-platform at HZI by Esther Surges. The compounds were dissolved in 750 µL of deuterated acetonitrile, acetone or chloroform, depending on their solubility, and transferred into 5 mm NMR tubes. The NMR spectra were then interpreted by Dr. Njogu Mark Kimani.

3.4.3 IR

To determine functional groups in molecules, infrared Spectroscopy was also used. Pure compounds were dissolved in ACN Uvasol® at the concentration of 20 mg/mL. All process was completed according to protocol.

3.4.4 UV/Vis absorption

To compare and characterize the isolated compounds, UV absorption of those were measured. A UV-2450 spectrophotometer (Shimadzu Corporation, Kyoto, Japan) was used to measure the UV absorbance properties of the isolated metabolites between 190 and 600 nm at 1 nm intervals to determine the maximum absorbance values of each compound. The compounds were dissolved in ACN and ACN Uvasol® at a final concentration of 0.1 - 0.05 mg/mL and transferred to a cuvette with 10 mm path length. The extinction coefficient of the absorbance maxima was calculated with the Beer-Lambert-Law as following:

$$\epsilon = \frac{A}{c \cdot l}$$

ε : molar extinction coefficient [$\frac{L}{mol \cdot cm}$]

A: Absorbance of the sample

c: Concentration of the sample [mol/L]

l: Path length of the cuvette [cm]

3.4.5 Optical rotation

Anton Paar MCP-150 circular polarimeter (Anton Paar Group AG, Graz, Austria) was used to measure the optical rotation. Calibration of the instrument was achieved using a quartz standard cell. The compounds were measured in chloroform Uvasol® at the temperature of 20°C. All samples were measured at a concentration of 10 mg/mL. The specific optical rotation was calculated through the following formula:

$$[\alpha]_D^T = \frac{\alpha \cdot 100}{c \cdot l}$$

$[\alpha]$: Specific optical rotation $[\frac{^\circ \cdot mL}{dm \cdot g}]$

T: Temperature (20°C)

D: Sodium D line (589 nm)

α : Observed optical rotation [°]

c: Concentration of the sample [g/100mL]

l: Path length of the sample cell (1dm)

3.4.6 Mosher's analysis

For deduction of the configuration of otherwise unknown stereogenic, secondary carbinol (alcohol) centers, Mosher test was done. 0.5 mg pure compounds were dissolved in 250 μ L, 10 μ L of R/S – Mosher reagent was added into the compounds and solvent mixture for incubating overnight (Hoye et al., 2007).

3.5 Bioactivity test

3.5.1 Antimicrobial and cytotoxicity assay

Antimicrobial and cytotoxic activity tests of the isolated compounds were completed by Wera Collisi at Helmholtz Centre for Infection Research. In total, 6 compounds were tested against seven cell lines to check its cytotoxicity. Bioactivity of these six compounds against seven bacterial strains and five additional fungal strains were accomplished. The antimicrobial assays were conducted in a serial dilution assay outlined by Harms et al. (2021). All tested organisms are listed in Table 6. Cytotoxic assay was performed according to Primahana et al. (2021) with the cell lines presented in Table 7. The IC₅₀ was determined through an MTT assay according to Becker et al. (2020). Antimicrobial and cytotoxic activity tests were not conducted on other compounds due to their limited amount.

Table 6: Organisms tested in antimicrobial assays.

Organism	Strain number
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	DSM 1116
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	DSM 10
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	DSM 346
<i>Mycobacterium smegmatis</i>	ATCC 700084
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	PA14
<i>Chromobacterium violaceum</i>	DSM 30191
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	DSM 30008
<i>Mucor hiemalis</i>	DSM 2656
<i>Schizosaccharomyces pombe</i>	DSM 70572
<i>Wickerhamomyces anomalus</i>	DSM 6766
<i>Candida albicans</i>	DSM 1665
<i>Rhodotorula glutinis</i>	DSM 10134

Table 7: Cell lines tested in cytotoxic assays.

Cell line	Type	Collection number
KB3-1	Human endocervical adenocarcinoma	ACC 158
L-929	Murine fibroblast	ACC 2
A-431	Human epidermoid carcinoma	ACC 91
MCF-7	Human breast adenocarcinoma	ACC 115
SKOV-3	Human ovary adenocarcinoma	HTB77
A-549	Human lung carcinoma	ACC 107
PC-3	Human prostate carcinoma	ACC 465

3.5.2 Biofilm Inhibitory Assay

Biofilm inhibition activities of **23**, **24**, **27**, **28**, **29** and **31** were evaluated for their inhibitory activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* (DSM 1104) according to protocol described previously with slight changes (Soliga et al. 2021). Briefly, a preculture of *S. aureus* (DSM 1104) was made from stock kept at -20° C. After 18 hours incubation, media suspension for biofilm assay was made and OD₆₀₀ of culture was adjusted to 0.001 McFarland standard. *S. aureus* was then incubated along with serially diluted compounds (66-0.5 µg/mL) to produce biofilms in 96 well micro titer plates for 24 h. For 7,

the concentration used was 31.25-125 µg/mL. Biofilm inhibition activity of compounds was assessed by crystal violet staining with subsequent washing steps and analyzing the stained biomass with the micro titer plate reader. Methanol was used as solvent control and taken as 100% with no inhibition activity against biofilm formation of *S. aureus*. Microporenic acid (MAA) was used as positive control (Chepkirui et al. 2018). All experiments were performed twice with duplicates. SD of two repeats with duplicates each was 15% or less.

4. Result

The cultivation of *N. nambi*, followed by the extraction, fractionation, and purification of its secondary metabolites, led to the identification of a total of 11 natural pure compounds. The structures of all isolated compounds were elucidated, and their bioactivities were assessed against selected fungi, bacteria and biofilm, as well as their cytotoxic effects on various cell lines. LC-MS analysis revealed the presence of all compounds in this strain at varying retention time. The results are displayed according to the chemical structures, Molar mass and molecular formulae (Table 9). Notably, four previously unknown compounds were isolated alongside metabolites previously reported in the literature.

Figure 6. Left: Fruiting body of *N. nambi* growing on bark of a tree in Arabuko Sokoke National Park, Malindi Kenya. PC: Hedda Schrey and Jan Peer Wennrich. Right: Culture of this fungus on solid YM 6.3 medium.

4.1 Production of secondary metabolites from *Neonothopanus nambi*

4.1.1 Small scale production of secondary metabolites.

Before scale-up fermentation, small scale fermentation of 9 different media were tested. An overview of chemical profiles of these seven media are shown below (Figure 8, 9, 10, 11). The harvest amount of compounds were measured before cartridge.

Scale-up fermentation was conducted using the YM 6.3 and SNL media. In ZM medium, *N. nambi* produced almost no UV-active compounds, while Q6 medium primarily yielded fatty acids. Across various media, LC-MS analysis showed similar compound masses and retention times. Notably, in the SYMglu and SNL media, *N. nambi* demonstrated substantial secondary metabolite productivity: SYMglu yielded 404.6 mg of crude extract from the supernatant and 272.66 mg from the mycelium, while SNL produced 689.79 mg from the supernatant and 99.79 mg from the mycelium. In contrast, productivity in the original SYM medium was low, yielding only 5.93 mg from the supernatant and 35.91 mg from the mycelium. Substituting sucrose with an equivalent amount of glucose significantly enhanced productivity. Compared to the YM medium (55.6% malt extract, 22.2% D-glucose, and 22.2% yeast extract), the SYM medium has similar components (66.7% malt extract, 22.2% sucrose, and 11.1% yeast extract) except for the sugar source and the percentage composition of each component (Figure 7).

Crude extract from CM medium were 26.39 mg (s), 56.05 mg (m); from GDYP medium were 152.26 mg (s), 74.56 mg (m), from YM medium were 82.57 mg (s) and 34.22 mg (m), from ZM medium were 61.57 mg (s) and 36.9 mg (m), from Q6 medium were 51.84 (s) and 15.9 mg (m). The crude extracts from rice solid medium without cartridge were 2.0626 g with some fatty acids.

Figure 7. 400 mL small scale fermentation in different media and its secondary metabolites productivity. Orange: The compounds productivity of mycelium; Blue: The compounds productivity of supernatant.

The UV signal of **25** was detected only in SYM and YM media, with a retention time of approximately 11 minutes, but was absent in SYMglu medium.

In GDYP medium (pH = 3), this strain also grew well, indicating its acidophilic profile. In GDYP, YM 6.3 (solid) and Rice media, only **28** was mainly produced. Only low-mass (under 300) secondary metabolites were produced in CM medium.

Figure 8. Secondary metabolites of *N. nambi* in SYMglu medium and SYM media.

Figure 9. Secondary metabolites of *N. nambi* in CM, GDYP and Rice media.

Figure 10. Secondary metabolites of *N. nambi* in SNL YM and Q6 media, a large mass is located on the upper side of the picture, while a smaller mass is positioned at the lower side.

A concise overview of the secondary metabolites produced during bacterial and fungal co-cultivation is outlined below. *Chitinophaga pinensis* has been found to exhibit high antifungal activity against numerous filamentous fungi and yeasts, though its antibacterial efficacy remains weak (Mohr et al. 2015). Notably, in co-cultivation with *N. nambi*, both this strain and *C. pinensis* demonstrated inhibitory effects. Under growth-inhibiting conditions, *N. nambi* produced only **28**, with no derivatives produced. Additionally, the production of low-mass secondary metabolites was markedly reduced. *N. nambi* may exhibit slight inhibitory effects against *C. pinensis*, as indicated by the limited growth spread (Figure 11). After 24 days of co-cultivation, *N. nambi* exhibited a color change on the plates containing only this strain, shifting from white to brown. Based on analysis from the Amazon platform, this darker coloration may indicate an increased production of **28** and its derivatives.

Figure 11. Secondary metabolites production of *Chitinophaga pinensis* *dsm* 2588 and *N. nambi* Co-culture.

4.1.2 Scale-up production of secondary metabolites.

In the first scale-up fermentation of *N. nambi* in YM 6.3 medium, mycelium and supernatant were extracted separately. Trial separations were performed using size exclusion chromatography, thin-layer chromatography, and preparative HPLC. The total amount of secondary metabolites obtained from 4 L cultures is shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Summary of the harvest in scale-up fermentation.

Description	Source	Amount of crude extract [mg]
First scale-up Fermentation in YM media	Mycelia in total	586.32 mg
	Supernatant in total	996.49 mg
First scale-up fermentation in SNL media	Combination of Mycelia and Supernatant	4213.57 mg
Second scale-up fermentation in YM media	Combination of Mycelia and Supernatant	2527.33 mg

Figure 12. First scale-up secondary metabolites of *N. nambi* in 4 L of YM 6.3 medium.

The second scale-up fermentation using SNL media and the YM media resulted in different secondary metabolite profiles due to varying fermentation conditions. Specifically, the scale of the flask, the volume of the media, and the oxygen availability in the flask differed during the second fermentation, which likely influenced the metabolic outputs. Aside from these factors, all other incubation conditions were kept consistent across both fermentations.

The secondary metabolites produced in the second scale-up fermentation mentioned above were summarized below. Given the significant overlap in the types of secondary metabolites found in both the mycelium and the supernatant, samples from both phases were combined for further analysis to provide a comprehensive overview of the metabolic profile.

Figure 13. 2nd. Secondary metabolites from 4.8 L Scale-up of *N. nambi* in YM 6.3 and 5 L 1st. Scale-up of *N. nambi* in SNL liquid media.

4.2 11 Isolated compounds from *Neonothopanus* sp.

All crude extracts from both supernatant and mycelia were first purified using preparative HPLC, followed by the recombination of all fractions. The final purification was completed through semi-preparative HPLC system.

Table 9: Compounds isolated from *N. nambi* CCC 1560.

Name	Molecular formula	Molar mass [g/mol]	Yield [mg]
Aurisin X (1)	C ₃₀ H ₃₈ O ₉	542.62	88,88
Aurisin Y (2)	C ₃₀ H ₄₀ O ₉	544.63	15,65
Aurisin W (3)	C ₃₁ H ₃₉ O ₉	554.63	1,41
Aurisin A (4)	C ₃₀ H ₃₆ O ₉	540.60	141.39
Nambinone C (5)	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O ₃	250.33	2.25
axinysone B (6)	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O ₂	234.33	1,1
Methyl 4-butyramidobenzoate (7)	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ NO ₃	221.25	2,19
Nambinone A (8)	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O ₃	250.33	10.64
axinysone A (9)	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O ₂	234.33	6,64

Methyl 4-(acetylamino)benzoate (10)	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ NO ₃	193.20	1.1
Aurisin Z (11)	C ₃₀ H ₃₆ O ₁₀	556.60	(unstable)

Among all the purified compounds, Compounds **1–3** were identified as novel derivatives of a previously reported compound known as aurisin (Charoenwongpaiboon et al. 2022), which was also isolated during the process and designated as aurisin A (**4**). In addition, known secondary metabolites were identified based on HR-ESI-MS and detailed 1D/2D NMR spectroscopic analyses along with comparison with the reported literature. These compounds were identified as, two monomeric sesquiterpene Nambinone C (**5**) and axinyson B (**6**), and one benzoate, Methyl 4-butyramidobenzoate (**7**) (Kanokmedhakul et al. 2012; Tsarkova et al. 2016; Kim et al. 2015). Compound **11** was also identified as new derivative of aurisin but found to be unstable and decomposed during the 2-dimensional NMR experiment in deuterated ACN.

Figure 14. Chemical structures of aurisin derivatives (dimeric sesquiterpenoids), benzoates and monomeric sesquiterpenoids from CCC 1560.

4.3 Spectral data

Compound **1** was obtained as light yellow powder; $[\alpha]_D^{20} = 0.1676^\circ$ (Chloroform, 10mg/mL); UV/Vis (Chloroform) : λ_{\max} (log ϵ) = 308 (0.561), 198 (0.570), 236.5 (0.153) nm; ESIMS: m/z 526.29 $[M-H_2O+H]^+$, $[M-H]^-$ 541.25; HRESIMS: m/z 543.2585 $[M+H]^+$ (calcd. 543.2585 for $C_{30}H_{39}O_9^+$), $t_R = 9.72$ min (LC-ESI-MS). $C_{30}H_{38}O_9$ (542.62 g/mol), with 12 degrees of unsaturation. The IR spectrum confirmed the presence of hydroxyl groups (3449.70 cm^{-1}) and conjugated ketone group (1677.19 cm^{-1}). Additionally, a C-H stretch was observed at 2973.13 cm^{-1} . Analysis of 1H and HSQC spectra indicated the presence of 8 methyl groups (δ 13.4, 14.0, 15.1, 15.7, 24.7, 25.8, 29.7 and 30.7), and 9 methine groups (δ 27.9, 32.5, 37.9, 38.0, 38.1, 40.1, 53.1, 53.8, 69.9) (Table 12). Analysis of ^{13}C NMR revealed the presence of 13 quaternary carbons (δ , 28.9, 38.0, 101.9, 112.0, 118.2, 120.2, 161.9, 174.4, 191.9, 201.7, 202.9). The COSY spectrum showed H-3/H-4/H15, H-3'/H-4'/H15', H-6/H-7/H-8 and H-6'/H-7' spin systems. The key HMBC correlations of **1** are shown below (Figure 16, 1). An analysis of the 1D and 2D NMR spectra indicated the structure of **1** was shown in appendix. The relative configuration of compound **1** was deduced through comparison of the NMR data to that reported for aurisin A (Kanokmedhakul et al. 2012) and from ROESY data. From the ROESY spectra, there was correlation between H-8 and H-7 indicating the orientation of these protons.

Compound **2** was isolated as white powder, $[\alpha]_D^{20} = 1.67$ (Chloroform, 10mg/mL); UV/Vis (Chloroform) : λ_{\max} (log ϵ) = 299 (0.966), 226.50 (0.078) nm; ESIMS: m/z 567.31 $[M+Na+H]^+$, 543.31 $[M-H]^-$; HRESIMS: m/z 545.2761 $[M+H]^+$, (calc. 545.2761 for $C_{30}H_{41}O_9^+$) $t_R = 9.59$ min (LC-ESI-MS). $C_{30}H_{40}O_9$ (544.63g/mol), indicating 11 degrees of unsaturation. The IR spectrum confirmed the presence of hydroxyl groups (3449.70 cm^{-1}) and conjugated ketone group (1677.19 cm^{-1}). The analysis of the NMR spectra indicated the presence of a symmetrical dimer. The monomeric unit 1H , HSQC and ^{13}C spectra analysis revealed the presence of four methyl groups (δ 12.8, 14.7, 24.2, and 29.9), the presence of five methine groups (δ 26.2, 31.4, 38.6, 51.2, and 69.1) and six quaternary carbons (δ 19.6, 37.4, 100.8, 110.3, 170.6, and 201.4,; Table 10). The 1H - 1H COSY spectrum showed H-3/H-4/H15 and H-6/H-7/H-8 spin systems. The HMBC correlations supported the structure of **2** as shown in figure 16, 2. The spectra of this compound differed from that of **1** by the presence of an extra hydroxyl group at C-8' (δ 69.1), indicating a reduction of the conjugated ketone in **1**.

Figure 15. Key HMBC correlations of **23** and **24**.

Compound **3** was isolated as yellow oil, determined to have an m/z 555.2593 from HRESIM corresponding to the molecular formula $C_{31}H_{39}O_9$ indicating 13 degrees of unsaturation. The analysis of the NMR spectra showed the presence of a methoxy group (δ 52.02, δ 3.34). The presence of a further eight methyl groups (δ 13.7, 14.6, 15.7, 15.8, 25.1, 26.2, 29.6, and 29.7), eight methine groups (δ 37.8, 37.9, 38.1, 38.2, 38.8, 38.9, 52.3 and 55.4,) and fourteen quaternary carbons (Table 10). The $1H-1H$ COSY spectrum showed spin systems as observed in compounds **1** and **2**. The HMBC correlations between the methoxy protons (δ 3.34) and C-2 (δ 103.4) indicated the methoxylation of the OH at position 2 in compounds **1** and **2**. The ^{13}C spectra indicate the presence of 4 ketone carbonyl groups (δ 191.6, 192.1, 199.2 and 199.8), one and two more in comparison with **1** and **2**, respectively. Therefore, the compound was unambiguously determined as shown in figure 17.

Figure 16. Chemical structure of Compound **3**.

Table 10: ¹H (500 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (125 MHz) data for **1**, **2**, **3** in Acetonitrile-d₃.

1			2		3	
No.	δ _c , type	δ _H (J in Hz)	δ _c , type	δ _H (J in Hz)	δ _c , type	δ _H (J in Hz)
1	191.8, C		201.4, C		191.6, C	
2	101.9, C		100.8, C		103.4, C	
3	54.0, CH	2.29, m	51.2, CH	2.33, m	55.4, CH	2.51, d, (12.27)
4	40.1, CH	2.26, dt (12.69, 6.27)	38.6, CH	2.29, m	38.9, CH	2.44, dq, (13.01, 6.51)
5	38.58, C		37.4, C		38.4, C	
6	32.5, CH	1.11, d (9.76)	31.4, CH	1.07, d	38.2, CH	1.70, d, (7.86)
7	26.9, CH	1.40, dd (9.76, 6.15)	26.2, CH	1.52, dd	37.8, CH	2.04, d(7.91)
8	69.8, CH	4.63, d (6.15)	69.1, CH	4.62, d	199.8, C	
9	174.9, C		170.61 C		162.7, C	
10	112.0, C		110.3, C		120.5, C	
11	20.7, C		19.6, C		28.8, C	
12	15.6, CH ₃	1.02, s	14.7, CH ₃	1.05, s	15.7, CH ₃	1.26-1.32, overlapped
13	30.5, CH ₃	1.09, s	29.9, CH ₃	1.11, s	29.7, CH ₃	1.26-1.32, overlapped
14	24.7, CH ₃	1.19, s	24.2, CH ₃	1.19, s	25.1, CH ₃	1.26-1.32, overlapped
15	13.4, CH ₃	1.15, d (6.43)	12.8, CH ₃	1.16, s	14.6, CH ₃	1.26-1.32, overlapped
1'	191.9, C		201.4, C		192.1, C	
2'	101.6, C		100.8, C		102.0, C	
3'	53.2, CH	2.38, m	51.2, CH	2.33, m	52.4, CH	2.38, d, (12.51)
4'	37.9, CH	2.45, m	38.6, CH	2.29, m	38.1, CH	2.26, dq, (12.55, 6.60)
5'	38.0		37.4, C		38.2, C	
6'	38.4, CH	1.64, d (7.90)	31.4, CH	1.07, d	38.8, CH	1.67, d, (7.96)
7'	37.8, CH	1.98, d (7.90)	26.2, CH	1.52, dd	37.8, CH	2.03, d, (7.98)
8'	201.6, C		69.1, CH	4.62, d	199.2, C	
9'	161.9, C		170.61 C		161.5, C	
10'	120.2, C		110.3, C		120.3, C	
11'	20.37, C		19.6, C		28.9, C	
12'	15.65, CH ₃	1.25, s	14.7, CH ₃	1.05, s	15.7, CH ₃	1.26-1.32, overlapped
13'	29.7, CH ₃	1.26, s	29.9, CH ₃	1.11, s	29.6, CH ₃	1.26-1.32, overlapped
14'	25.8, CH ₃	1.17, s	24.2, CH ₃	1.19, s	26.3, CH ₃	1.26-1.32, overlapped
15'	14.0, CH ₃	1.22, d (6.67)	12.8, CH ₃	1.16, s	13.7, CH ₃	1.26-1.32, overlapped
OH						5.07, s
OCH ₃						3.34, s

4.4 Bioactivity of pure isolated compounds.

4.4.1 Antimicrobial and cytotoxic assay

The bioactivity against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, fungi, various human and murine cell lines was evaluated in line with the methodology described in section 3.5. A restricted quantity of compounds **3**, **8**, **9**, **10** and **11** precluded their assessment in both the cytotoxic and antimicrobial assays. The antimicrobial and cytotoxic activities of the isolated compounds are presented in Table 11. No compounds exhibited potent antifungal activity. Compounds **1**, **2** and **4** displayed cytotoxic effects against the K-3-1, L-929, MCF-7, A-549 and PC-3 cell line besides microbial activity against

Staphylococcus aureus and *Bacillus subtilis*. Three compounds noted the significant inhibition activity against *Bacillus subtilis* (MIC values are 2.0, 2.0 and 4.1 respectively) and weaker inhibition activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* at MIC value 16.6, 8.3, 8.3 correspondingly. Compounds **5**, **6** and **7** displayed slight cytotoxic effects against L-929 and MCF-7 cell lines without antimicrobial activity.

Table 11. Cytotoxic and antimicrobial activity of compounds 1, 2, 5, 6, 7, 9

Test Cell line	IC ₅₀ [μM]						Positive Control
	1	2	7	4	5	6	Epithilone B [nM]
Human endocervical adenocarcinoma (KB-3-1)	0.51	0.33	n.d.	0.25	n.d.	n.d.	0.17
Mouse fibroblast (L-929)	22.0	7	>37	22	>37	>37	0.65
Human epidermoid carcinoma (A-431)	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	0.06
Human breast adenocarcinoma (MCF-7)	0.13	0.1	23.0	0.17	>37	>37	0.07
Human ovarian cancer (SKOV-3)	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	0.09
Human lung carcinoma (A-549)	1.8	1.3	n.d.	1.8	n.d.	n.d.	0.05
Human prostate carcinoma (PC-3)	0.6	0.72	n.d.	1.3	n.d.	n.d.	0.09

Test Microorganism	MIC[μg/mL]						Positive Control
	1	2	7	4	5	6	
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (DSM 1116)	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	0.42 ^G
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> (DSM 10)	2.0	2.0	n.i.	4.1	n.i.	n.i.	16.6 ^O
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (DSM 346)	16.6	8.3	n.i.	8.3	n.i.	n.i.	0.21 ^G
<i>Mycobacterium smegmatis</i> (ATCC 700084)	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	1.70 ^K
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> (PA14)	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	0.21 ^G
<i>Chromobacterium violaceum</i> (DSM 30191)	n.i.	66.6	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	1.70 ^G
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i> (DSM 30008)	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	0.52 ^C
<i>Mucor hiemalis</i> (DSM 2656)	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	8.30 ^N
<i>Schizosaccharomyces pombe</i> (DSM 70572)	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	8.30 ^N
<i>Wickerhamomyces anomalus</i> (DSM 6766)	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	16.6 ^N
<i>Candida albicans</i> (DSM 1665)	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	8.30 ^N
<i>Rhodotorula glutinis</i> (DSM 10134)	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	4.20 ^N

n.i.: no inhibition up to 67 μg/mL. n.d.: not determined. A: Amphotericin G: Gentamycin; O: Oxytetracycline; N: Nystatin; C: Ciprofloxacin; K: Kanamycin

4.4.2 Biofilm Inhibitory Assay

After cytotoxicity and MIC test, the compounds **1,2** and **4-7** were tested against biofilms of *S. aureus* in biofilm inhibition assay. Compound **5** was tested in different concentration scales (table 12). At the concentration of 31.25 μg/mL, it shows 33% inhibition of biofilm.

Table 12: Biofilm inhibition activity of compound 5

Concentration	Inhibition (%)	SD
125 µg/mL	78	±0.082893506
62.5 µg/mL	79	±0.085052925
31.25 µg/mL	33	±0.085052925

The results of the biofilm inhibition assay against *Staphylococcus aureus* demonstrated potent activity of two novel aurisin derivatives, X (**1**) and Y (**2**), which exhibited superior efficacy compared to the previously reported aurisin A (**4**). Compound **1** effectively inhibited 73% of biofilm formation at a concentration of 2 µg/mL, while compound **2** achieved same level of inhibition at 1 µg/mL. In contrast, aurisin A displayed activity up to a concentration of 4 µg/mL, with an 80% inhibition of *S. aureus* biofilms.

Figure 17. *S. aureus* biofilm inhibition by aurisin X (**1**), Y (**2**) and A (**4**). Microporenic acid A (MAA) was used as a positive control. Methanol was used as a solvent control and taken as 100%. Error bars indicate standard deviation (SD) of duplicates in two biological repeats.

5. Discussion

In this study, in total 11 secondary metabolites were isolated. These compounds exhibit a diverse spectrum of chemical structures, including five sesquiterpenoid dimers in which three were new aurisin derivatives (**1-3**). Compound **11**, one of the aurisin derivative, was decomposed during 2D-NMR test; further analysis was not possible. Two benzoates (**7** and **10**), as well as four monomeric sesquiterpenoids (**5,6,8** and **9**).

Tsarkova et al. (2016) identified nambiscalarane and other secondary metabolites from *N. nambi*. Compound **7** was determined as a disubstituted amine containing benzoic acid (PABA), which was identified as a growth factor in many bacterial species and might be a primitive form of antibiotic to inhibit the metabolism of PABA in bacteria. **7** was identified as a disubstituted amine containing a benzoic acid moiety, derived from p-aminobenzoic acid (PABA). It is considered to exist in an acidic form in nature, with esterification likely occurring during the extraction process. Despite showing weak activity against the mouse fibroblast cell line (L-929) and human breast adenocarcinoma cell line (MCF-7), this compound holds potential value for the treatment of human breast cancer.

Compound **5** showed weak antimalarial activity at $IC_{50} > 20 \mu\text{M}$, no significant antituberculosis activity at $IC_{50} > 100$. Its cytotoxicity against NCI-H187 cell lines with IC_{50} values of 16.42 but without the activity against L-929 cell line, showed the potential as a drug in cancer treatment. (Kanoknedhakul et al., 2012). In this thesis, the cytotoxicity against L-929, MCF-7 were both reported at $IC_{50} > 37$.

9 has been found as a naturally occurring sesquiterpenoid isolated from marine sources such as the alga *Laurencia similis* and from the metabolites of the mushroom *Anthracoephyllum sp. BCC18695*. It has shown antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* at $IC_{50} = 50$ and *Streptococcus pyrogenes* at $IC_{50} = 20$, without cytotoxicity against Human breast cancer cell MCF-7, Human cervical cancer cell line Hela, Murine (mouse) leukemia cell line P388 and Human T-cell leukemia ATL (Zubía et al., 2008, Kamada et al., 2013). In this thesis, **9** had no biological inhibition activity against tested microorganisms but showed cytotoxicity against the mouse fibroblast cell line L-929 and Human breast adenocarcinoma MCF-7 at $IC_{50} > 37$.

Time kill study against MRSA ATCC 33591 of aurisin A (**4**) has been identified that it effectively killed the MRSA strain after 1 hour compared to the kill time about 8 hours of vancomycin at the 5 times and 10 times MIC concentration, indicating the MRSA killing rate of aurisin A was strongly higher than vancomycin. Compound **4** was also considered having potential different mechanisms of action against clinical *S.aureus* strains from fusidic acid (Krishnasamy et al. 2023). The rapid eradication time of pathogen may reduce the potential of resistance development (Ng et al. 2017). Compound **4** has been noted that it has profound cytotoxicity against cancer cells. An investigation of the anticancer effect of aurisin A was also accomplished by Boueroy (2020), aurisin A exerts its anticancer effects by inhibiting cell growth, increasing the proportion of cells at the G0/G1 phase, and decreasing the expression of cyclin D and cyclin-dependent kinase 4 (Cdk-4). Nuclear morphological changes were observed in aurisin A-treated cells, demonstrated increasing in the number of apoptosis cells by certain dose. In addition, inhibition of migration of cancer cells by this compound has also been reported.

1 and **2** showed significant higher biofilm inhibition activity than **4** but with lower or same antibacterial activity against planktonic cells of *S. aureus* (Table 11). The poor solubility of compound **4** in water (Charoenwongpaiboon et al. 2022) could be suggested as a reason for its preference to bind with biofilm components. However, the mechanism of compound **4** against biofilm and planktonic bacterial cells is still not clear. Compound **1** and **2** share structural similarity with **4**, suggesting they may also exhibit similar characteristics. Compared to compound **4**, the additional hydroxyl groups in **1** and **2** are particularly important in altering their chemical properties.

1, **2** and **4** were separated through column Nucleodur Phenyl-Hexyl_RP (250*40 mm, 5µm) through Gilson, the UV signal showed well separated result of these adjacent signal peaks. But the result from Amazon noted the impurity as showed below. After several times of nitrogen evaporation at 37 or 40 degrees, the percentage of impurity went higher.

Figure 18: The impurity after separation through semi-preparative HPLC. Number noted the compound number. The picture shown above showed **6** as impurity, the picture below showed **1** as impurity.

Not all the compounds could be tested in bioassays because of the limited amounts.

6. Outlook and Conclusions

In summary, this study emphasizes the significance of fungi like *Neonothopanus nambi* as a source of metabolites with antifungal, antibacterial, anticancer properties. Through the fermentation of different media followed by extraction, HPLC chromatography and subsequent structure elucidation, a total of 11 different compounds were characterized and their biological activities assessed.

The similar chemical structure of four different sesquiterpenoids and aurisin derivatives may reveal their chemical synthesis, which may contribute to further large-scale synthesis for industry use. The mechanism of aurisin is not clear now, but the higher inhibition of biofilm than planktonic cell inhibition may show the clue of another inhibition mechanism.

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9.3 Co-culture of *Chitinophaga pinensis* and *Neonothopanus nambi*.

Figure 1. A co-cultivation was performed on GYM agar plates, photos were collected on 19.04.2024, and these plates were prepared by Nina, as part of the co-culture inhibition analysis between *C. pinensis* and *N. nambi*.

Figure 2. A co-cultivation was performed on GYM agar plates, photos were collected on 29.04.2024, and these plates were prepared by Nina, as part of the co-culture inhibition analysis between *C. pinensis* and *N. nambi*.

Figure 3. A co-cultivation was performed on GYM agar plates, photos were collected on 06.05.2024, and these plates were prepared by Nina, as part of the co-culture inhibition analysis between *C. pinensis* and *N. nambi*.

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Figure 6. A mono-fungal cultivation was performed on GYM agar plates, prepared by Nina, as part of the co-culture inhibition analysis between *C. pinensis* and *N. nambi*.

Figure 7. A mono-bacterial cultivation was performed on GYM agar plates, prepared by Nina, as part of the co-culture inhibition analysis between *C. pinensis* and *N. nambi*.

9.4 Separation process

Figure 8. The whole extraction process.

9.5 HPLC-condition of isolated pure compounds summary

Before further purification and separation of crude extracts in HPLC system, a separation of small mass secondary metabolites and large mass secondary metabolites of mycelium was done during SPE cartridge process, detailed condition was shown in the table below.

Supernatant cartridge through 40%ACN was failed, mixture contained large amount of LMSM, thus all supernatant was collected again through ACT from 4mL vials into round bottom flask, evaporating all the ACT until only water phase left, using XAD beads to collect all the compounds again, later all the XAD beads were through 20% ACN washed and SMSM and LMSM were separated.

Table 1: Gradient for the initial scale-up of supernatant separation using a glass column for direct washing of XAD beads.

Parameter	Description
Sample name	Small mass secondary metabolites and large mass secondary metabolites separation
System	Sea sand, secondary metabolites bound with XAD beads
Column	Glass separation column
Flow rate	The flow rate is controlled manually, drop by drop, with the solvent in the SPE column covering the sand.
Sample amount	Supernatant in total 996.49 mg
Solvent	Isocratic washing, 20%/40%/100%ACN, 100%MeOH, 100%ACT with deionized water
Isolated Fraction	Fs I: water; Fs II: 20%ACN; Fs III: 40% ACN; Fs IV: 100% ACN; Fs V: 100% MeOH; Fs VI: 100% ACT

Table 2: Gradient for the initial scale-up of mycelium separation using a SPE cartridge column column for direct washing of XAD beads.

Parameter	Description
Sample name	Small mass secondary metabolites and large mass secondary metabolites separation
System	Sea sand + XAD beads with secondary metabolites + 20%ACN + 80% deionized water
Column	SPE Cartridge column
Flow rate	The flow rate is controlled manually, drop by drop, with the solvent in the SPE column covering the filtrate.
Sample amount	Mycelium in total 586.32 mg
Solvent	Isocratic washing, ACT, ACN, MeOH, deionized water
Isolated Fraction	Fm I: water; Fm II: 40%ACN; Fm III: 100% ACN; Fm IV: 100% MeOH; Fm V: 100% ACT

Table 3: Preparative RP-HPLC separation parameters used to isolate crude extract Fm IV: 100% MeOH; Fs V: 100% MeOH (combined analysis) from first scale-up YM6.3 medium fermentation.

Parameter	Description		
Sample name	Fm IV: 100% MeOH; Fs V: 100% MeOH (combined analysis)		
System	Gilson PLC 2050		
Column	A_S4 Nucleolus Phenyl-Hexyl_RP (250 x 40 mm, 5 µm)		
Flow rate	40 mL/min		
SCAN Signal: 200-800nm	Signal 2: 254 nm	Signal 3: 280 nm	
	Signal 4: 300 nm	Signal 5: 330 nm	
Elution gradient	Solvent A	Solvent B	
0	80%	20%	

15:00	50%	50%
47:09	35%	65%
54:06	14%	86%
01:05:00	00%	100%

Table 4: Preparative RP-HPLC separation parameters used to isolate crude extract (Fs III: 40% ACN; Fs IV: 100% ACN) from first scale-up YM6.3 medium fermentation.

Parameter	Description	
Sample name	Fs III: 40% ACN; Fs IV: 100% ACN	
System	Gilson PLC 2050	
Column	A_S4 Nucleolus Phenyl-Hexyl_RP (250 x 40 mm, 5 µm)	
Flow rate	40 mL/min	
SCAN Signal: 200-800nm	Signal 2: 254 nm	Signal 3: 280 nm
	Signal 4: 300 nm	Signal 5: 330 nm
Elution gradient	Solvent A	Solvent B
0	90%	10%
15:00	60%	40%
35:00	45%	55%
55:00	45%	55%
01:05:00	00%	100%

Table 5: Preparative RP-HPLC separation parameters used to isolate crude extract (Fm II: 40% ACN) from first scale-up YM6.3 medium fermentation.

Parameter	Description	
Sample name	Fm II: 40%ACN	
System	Gilson PLC 2050	
Column	A_S4 Nucleolus Phenyl-Hexyl_RP (250 x 40 mm, 5 µm)	
Flow rate	40 mL/min	
SCAN Signal: 200-800nm	Signal 2: 210 nm	Signal 3: 270 nm
	Signal 4: 300 nm	Signal 5: 330 nm
Elution gradient	Solvent A	Solvent B
0	70%	30%
10:00	60%	40%
30:00	50%	50%
45:00	35%	65%
55:00	30%	70%
01:15:00	0%	100%
01:20:00	0%	100%

Table 6: Preparative RP-HPLC separation parameters used to isolate crude extract (Fm III: 100% ACN) from first scale-up YM6.3 medium fermentation.

Parameter	Description	
Sample name	Fm III: 100% ACN	
System	Gilson PLC 2050	
Column	A_S4 Nucleolus Phenyl-Hexyl_RP (250 x 40 mm, 5 µm)	
Flow rate	40 mL/min	
SCAN Signal: 200-800nm	Signal 2: 280 nm	Signal 3: 200 nm
	Signal 4: 330 nm	Signal 5: 350 nm
Elution gradient	Solvent A	Solvent B
0	80%	20%
18:20	55%	45%
01:00:00	55%	45%

01:06:00	5%	95%
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Table 7: Size chromatographical separation parameters used to isolate crude extract Fs II: 20%ACN; Fm I: water; (combined analysis) from first scale-up YM6.3 medium fermentation.

Parameter	Description
Sample name	Fs II: 20%ACN; Fm I: water; (combined analysis)
System	ÄKRA pure, Cytiva Opti Run™ Sevicees
Column	Glass column fulfilled with Sephadex® LH-20
Flow rate	3 mL/min
Solvent	100% MeOH
Detection Signal	Signal 1: 230 ± 5 nm
	Signal 2: 270 ± 5 nm
UV signal detection time	Signal 3: 300 ± 5 nm
	Signal 4: 330 ± 5 nm
Elution gradient	Solvent
Isocratic	100% MeOH

Table 8: Preparative RP-HPLC separation parameters used to isolate crude extract from small-scale, 1st. Up-scale SNL and 2nd. YM fermentation.

Parameter	Description
Sample name	Small-scale, 1 st . Up-scale SNL and 2 nd . YM fermentation (supernatant and mycelium combined)
System	Gilson PLC 2050
Column	A_E3 Waters X-Bridge C18 (250 x 19 mm, 5 µm)
Flow rate	35 mL/min
SCAN Signal: 200-800nm	Signal 2: 230 nm
	Signal 3: 254 nm
Elution gradient	Signal 4: 300 nm
	Signal 5: 330 nm
	Solvent A
	Solvent B
00	80%
10:02	70%
18:11	68%
01:00:10	60%
02:00:00	00%
02:10:00	00%

Table 9: Semi-preparative RP-HPLC separation parameters used to isolate pure compounds **1** and **2**.

Parameter	Description
Sample name	Compound 1 and 2
System	Agilent Technologies 1200 series
Column	Waters X-Bridge C18 (250*10 mm, 5 µm)
Flow rate	3 mL/min
Solvent	ACN, deionized water
Detection Signal	Signal 1: 230 ± 5 nm
	Signal 2: 270 ± 5 nm
UV signal detection time	Signal 3: 300 ± 5 nm
	Signal 4: 330 ± 5 nm
Elution gradient	Pure 507+: 34-38 min
	Pure 509+: 31-32.5 min
	Solvent A
	Solvent B
Isocratic	61% deionized water
	39% ACN

Table 10: Semi-preparative RP-HPLC separation parameters used to isolate pure compounds **3**.

Parameter	Description
Sample name	Compound 3 (collected from yellow rest from Gilson)
System	Gilson

Column	Nucleodur Phenyl-Hexyl_RP (250*40 mm, 5 μ m)	
Flow rate	3 mL/min	
Solvent	ACN, deionized water + 0.1% FA	
Isolated Fraction	1.41 mg	
Detection Signal range: 200-800nm	Signal 1: 230 \pm 5 nm	Signal 2: 280 \pm 5 nm
	Signal 3: 300 \pm 5 nm	Signal 4: 330 \pm 5 nm
UV signal detection time	collected from yellow rest from Gilson	No detailed retention time
Elution gradient	Solvent A	Solvent B
Increasing gradient	61% deionized water	39% ACN

Table 11: Semi-preparative RP-HPLC separation parameters used to isolate pure compounds **11**.

Parameter	Description	
Sample name	Compound 11	
System	Agilent Technologies 1200 series	
Column	Waters X-Bridge C18 (250*10 mm, 5 μ m)	
Flow rate	3 mL/min	
Solvent	ACN, deionized water + 0.1% FA	
Detection Signal	Signal 1: 230 \pm 5 nm	Signal 2: 270 \pm 5 nm
	Signal 3: 300 \pm 5 nm	Signal 4: 330 \pm 5 nm
UV signal detection time	15min – 17,5 min	
Elution gradient	Solvent A	Solvent B
Isocratic	61% deionized water	39% ACN

Table 12: Semi-preparative RP-HPLC separation parameters used to isolate pure compounds **7**.

Parameter	Description	
Sample name	Compound 7	
System	Agilent Technologies 1200 series	
Column	Waters X-Bridge C18 (250*10 mm, 5 μ m)	
Flow rate	3 mL/min	
Solvent	ACN and deionized water	
Isolated Fraction	F(4): 1,92 mg	
Detection Signal	Signal 1: 230 \pm 5 nm	Signal 2: 270 \pm 5 nm
	Signal 3: 300 \pm 5 nm	Signal 4: 330 \pm 5 nm
UV signal detection time	17 - 18.5 min	
Elution gradient	Solvent A	Solvent B
Isocratic	65% deionized water	35% ACN

Table 13: Semi-preparative RP-HPLC separation parameters used to isolate pure compounds **5**.

Parameter	Description	
Sample name	Compound 5	
System	Agilent Technologies 1200 series	
Column	Waters X-Bridge C18 (250*10 mm, 5 μ m)	
Flow rate	3 mL/min	
Solvent	ACN, deionized water + 0.1% FA	
Detection Signal	Signal 1: 230 \pm 5 nm	Signal 2: 270 \pm 5 nm
	Signal 3: 300 \pm 5 nm	Signal 4: 330 \pm 5 nm
UV signal detection time	9 min – 9.6 min	
Elution gradient	Solvent A	Solvent B
Isocratic	70% deionized water	30% ACN

Table 14: Semi-preparative RP-HPLC separation parameters used to isolate pure compounds **8**.

Parameter	Description	
Sample name	Compound 8	
System	Agilent Technologies 1200 series	
Column	Waters X-Bridge C18 (250*10 mm, 5 µm)	
Flow rate	3 mL/min	
Solvent	ACN, deionized water + 0.1% FA	
Detection Signal	Signal 1: 230 ± 5 nm	Signal 2: 270 ± 5 nm
	Signal 3: 300 ± 5 nm	Signal 4: 330 ± 5 nm
UV signal detection time	6.5 min – 8 min	
Elution gradient	Solvent A	Solvent B
Isocratic	70% deionized water	30% ACN

Table 15: Semi-preparative RP-HPLC separation parameters used to isolate pure compounds **9**.

Parameter	Description	
Sample name	Compound 9	
System	Agilent Technologies 1200 series	
Column	Waters X-Bridge C18 (250*10 mm, 5 µm)	
Flow rate	3 mL/min	
Solvent	ACN and deionized water	
Isolated Fraction	F(1): 6,64mg	
Detection Signal	Signal 1: 230 ± 5 nm	Signal 2: 270 ± 5 nm
	Signal 3: 300 ± 5 nm	Signal 4: 330 ± 5 nm
UV signal detection time	21,5 – 23,5 min	
Elution gradient	Solvent A	Solvent B
Isocratic	65% deionized water	35% ACN

Table 16: Semi-preparative RP-HPLC separation parameters used to isolate pure compounds **6**.

Parameter	Description	
Sample name	Compound 6	
System	Agilent Technologies 1200 series	
Column	Waters X-Bridge C18 (250*10 mm, 5 µm)	
Flow rate	3 mL/min	
Solvent	ACN and deionized water	
Isolated Fraction	F(2): 1.1 mg	
Detection Signal	Signal 1: 230 ± 5 nm	Signal 2: 270 ± 5 nm
	Signal 3: 300 ± 5 nm	Signal 4: 330 ± 5 nm
UV signal detection time	16,5 -17,75min	
Elution gradient	Solvent A	Solvent B
Isocratic	65% deionized water	35% ACN

Table 17: Semi-preparative RP-HPLC separation parameters used to isolate pure compounds **10**.

Parameter	Description	
Sample name	Compound 10	
System	Agilent Technologies 1200 series	
Column	Waters X-Bridge C18 (250*10 mm, 5 µm)	
Flow rate	3 mL/min	
Solvent	ACN, deionized water + 0.1% FA	
Detection Signal	Signal 1: 230 ± 5 nm	Signal 2: 270 ± 5 nm
	Signal 3: 300 ± 5 nm	Signal 4: 330 ± 5 nm
UV signal detection time	7.8 min – 8.4 min	
Elution gradient	Solvent A	Solvent B
Isocratic	72% deionized water	28% ACN

9.6 IR, UV spectra of compounds 1 and 2

Figure 9. IR result of 23.

Figure 10. IR result of 24.

Figure 11. 23 dissolved in ACN Uvasol® at the concentration of 0.025mg/mL.

Figure 12. 24 dissolved in ACN Uvasol® at the concentration of 0.025mg/mL.

9.7 NMR-spectra of pure compounds

Figure 13: ^1H -NMR spectrum of **23** in acetonitrile- d_3 at 500 MHz.

Figure 14: ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of **23** in acetonitrile- d_3 at 125 MHz.

Figure 15: ^1H - ^1H COSY spectrum of **23** in acetonitrile- d_3 at 500 MHz.

Figure 16: HMBC spectrum of **23** in acetonitrile- d_3 at 500 MHz.

Figure

17: HSQC spectrum of **23** in acetonitrile-d₃ at 500 MHz.

Figure 18: ^1H -NMR spectrum of **24** in chloroform-*d* at 500 MHz.

Figure 19: ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of **24** in chloroform-*d* at 125 MHz.

Figure 20: COSY spectrum of **24** in chloroform-d at 500 MHz.

Figure 21: HMBC spectrum of **24** in chloroform-d at 500 MHz.

Figure 22: HSQC spectrum of **24** in chloroform-d at 500 MHz.

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